

Data Manipulation Attack Mitigation in Power Systems Using Physics-Informed Neural Networks

Solon Falas
ECE Dept., KIOS CoE
University of Cyprus
Nicosia, Cyprus
falas.solon@ucy.ac.cy

Markos Asprou
KIOS CoE
University of Cyprus
Nicosia, Cyprus
asprou.markos@ucy.ac.cy

Charalambos Konstantinou
CEMSE Division
KAUST
Thuwal, Saudi Arabia
charalambos.konstantinou@kaust.edu.sa

Maria K. Michael
ECE Dept., KIOS CoE
University of Cyprus
Nicosia, Cyprus
mmichael@ucy.ac.cy

Abstract—The growing digitalization of power transmission systems has introduced vulnerabilities to cyberattacks, particularly sensor manipulation, which can compromise control center monitoring and control applications. Conventional monitoring methods, including traditional state estimation and data-driven machine learning approaches, may face challenges in maintaining accuracy and reliability when confronted with such attacks. This paper proposes a physics-informed neural network (PINN)-based state estimation model to enhance robustness. By embedding power system physics, the PINN approach leverages both data-driven insights and physical constraints, improving robustness and accuracy in case of cyberattacks. The model’s performance is evaluated under diverse attack scenarios, comparing it to an equivalently sophisticated purely data-driven machine learning model. The results show that the PINN-based approach significantly improves robustness and accuracy, with or without the presence of attacks, offering a promising solution for robustifying power grid state estimation.

Index Terms—Power system, state estimation, robustness, cyberattacks, data manipulation, physics-informed, neural networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of digital technologies in power transmission systems has significantly enhanced operational efficiency and grid stability. However, this digital transformation has also exposed critical infrastructure to cybersecurity threats, particularly attacks that exploit vulnerabilities in state estimation processes [1]. These attacks manipulate sensor data to mislead power system operators, potentially leading to power outages, or cascading failures [2]. Given the role of state estimation in power systems, developing robust mitigation strategies against such threats is a pressing research challenge.

Traditional State Estimation (SE) techniques, such as the weighted least squares (WLS) method, assume data integrity and are vulnerable to well-crafted attacks that bypass conventional bad data detection (BDD) mechanisms. Existing security measures, including statistical anomaly detection and rule-based approaches, often fail to generalize against adaptive adversaries [3], [4]. Machine learning defenses show promise but often lack physical interpretability, leaving them vulnerable to adversarial attacks and distribution shifts [5].

Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) have emerged as a powerful paradigm that integrates physical laws into

machine learning models, improving their robustness and interpretability [6]. By embedding power system equations into neural network architectures, PINNs ensure that predictions adhere to fundamental grid physics, reducing the likelihood of erroneous state estimates caused by adversarial manipulations. This approach enhances robustness by leveraging both data-driven insights and physical constraints, making it well-suited for securing power system state estimation against such events.

Despite the potential of PINNs in power system applications, their robustness against cybersecurity threats remains largely unexplored. Prior works have primarily focused on PINNs for improving numerical simulations and solving differential equations, with limited emphasis on the implications for critical infrastructure protection [7]. A thorough evaluation of PINNs under attack scenarios, along with a comparative analysis of their performance against conventional techniques and purely data-driven neural networks, is essential to assess the real-world viability of this approach. Furthermore, investigating the impact of varying attack strategies and magnitudes on PINN performance is crucial for understanding their practical applicability in safeguarding power systems.

This paper presents a PINN-based architecture aimed at improving robustness to cybersecurity threats in power transmission systems. The main contributions are:

- Development of a PINN model trained on steady-state power system data, incorporating physical constraints to improve accuracy and robustness against adversarial inputs.
- Systematic evaluation of the model against diverse attack scenarios, including varying magnitudes and strategies, assessing its robustness compared to data-driven approaches.

The proposed PINN-based approach demonstrates the potential to enhance the security of power grids. By integrating physical principles into advanced machine learning models, this approach enables accurate and timely state estimation while being robust against erroneous input data.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews existing research. Section IV describes the proposed methodology, detailing the PINN architecture and training process. Section V provides experimental results, in-

cluding performance comparisons and robustness assessments. Finally, Section VI concludes and outlines future research.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

State Estimation forms the foundation for real-time monitoring and control of modern power systems, providing critical insights into system conditions by processing redundant measurements from devices like Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) and Remote Terminal Units (RTUs) [8]. The SE procedure works by solving the nonlinear relationship between the measurement vector z and the state vector x through a function $h(x)$ with measurement noise e :

$$z = h(x) + e \quad \hat{x} = \arg \min_x \|z - h(x)\|^2 \quad r = \|z - h(\hat{x})\|_\infty$$

where \hat{x} represents the estimated state vector, and r denotes the residual. In practice, this procedure first collects measurements from distributed sensors, then formulates a nonlinear optimization problem to find the most likely system state given these observations, and finally evaluates result quality through residual analysis. Traditional methods like WLS rely on the fundamental assumption of measurement integrity, but this assumption fails when facing malicious data manipulation [9].

Sophisticated measurement manipulation strategies exploit SE vulnerabilities by introducing a carefully crafted attack vector a into the measurement vector, resulting in compromised measurements $z_{\text{bad}} = z + a$ and a distorted state estimate $\hat{x}_{\text{bad}} = \hat{x} + c$, where c represents the induced estimation error. These malicious manipulations pose significant risks to grid stability and security, potentially causing cascading failures. While traditional advanced data tampering techniques required comprehensive knowledge of grid topology and line parameters, recent advancements demonstrate that limited PMU data can suffice to construct effective attack vectors [2]. Techniques such as leveraging ambient load dynamics and utilizing the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process enable malicious actors to estimate system parameters and design stealthy, targeted manipulations with minimal information.

Current defense mechanisms, like statistical anomaly detection and rule-based BDD systems, struggle against adaptive adversaries [9]. Although robust estimation methods like Weighted Least Absolute Value (WLAV) and Maximum Exponential Square (MES) proved useful, evolving adversarial strategies necessitate more resilient solutions. Machine Learning (ML) approaches to counter such malicious data manipulations have shown promise, but purely data-driven models frequently lack robustness against adversarial attacks and may not generalize well under dynamic conditions [10].

PINNs have seen growing use in power system state estimation, with promising results demonstrated using advanced models like graphical neural networks [11], [12]. While [13] briefly assessed robustness to limited adversarial perturbations using adversarial training, our approach does not rely on such methods. Instead, we present a comprehensive evaluation across the entire power system, rather than isolated components. To our knowledge, this is the first study assessing PINN robustness against adversarial data manipulation.

III. THREAT MODEL

In this work, we consider a threat model where an attacker is able to manipulate active and reactive power values, denoted as P and Q , respectively. The attacker's objective is to influence the SE procedure by introducing an attack vector a into the state estimation SE process.

The manipulated measurement vector can be represented as:

$$z_{\text{bad}} = z + a, \quad (1)$$

where z is the original measurement vector, and a is the crafted attack vector derived from changes in P and Q at the compromised bus. This results in a false estimated state:

$$x_{\text{bad}} = x + c, \quad (2)$$

where x is the original estimated state, and c is the state estimation error introduced by the attack. By controlling the P/Q values, the attacker can construct an attack vector a that alters the estimated values of a SE model in order to influence the behavior of the power system under attack.

The primary goal of the proposed model is to mitigate or minimize the impact of a on the SE results. This can be achieved by minimizing the state estimation error c , without explicitly training the model for that purpose. Instead, the model should be able to provide more accurate inferred SE values due to the physics-based constraints imposed during the training process.

A. Attack Vector Construction

To put this hypothesis to test, a comprehensive testing dataset was constructed. The objectives of the testing dataset were (a) to simulate a comprehensive set of various attacks in terms of location and implementation, and (b) to ensure that the dataset reflects different magnitudes of data tampering for examining their effect on the SE accuracy of the models.

Monte Carlo sampling is utilized to generate the attack vectors z_{bad} , which represent multiple copies of an unknown testing dataset z . The unknown dataset z is modified using a modification factor a , simulating various attack scenarios on power system measurements. The process is as follows:

- The modification factors' behavior is first chosen randomly between four different combinations: increase or decrease the original P values, and increase or decrease the original Q values.
- A static multiplier is then selected to determine the magnitude of the modification factor, a percentage deviation from the true value.
- A random bus is selected as the attack target.
- The random modification factors a are applied to the P and Q , representing changes in power injections.

Let \mathbf{z} be the vector representing the measurements P/Q of each bus. An attack vector for Bus N can be constructed as:

$$\mathbf{z}_{\text{bad}} = \mathbf{z}[:, N] \times a \quad (3)$$

where a is the modification factor that represents the magnitude of the attack (e.g., $a = 1.05$ or $a = 0.95$ for a 5% attack,

depending on the random increase or decrease). To verify the distribution of the chosen buses, the observed frequency of attacks on each bus was compared with the expected frequency under a uniform distribution. A constraint was applied that these frequencies should not deviate by more than 5%, which corresponds approximately to maintaining a p-value above 0.05 in the chi-square goodness-of-fit test. This ensures that no statistically significant biases were introduced by unevenly targeting specific buses in the network.

IV. PINN MODEL DESIGN

PINNs embed physical laws directly into neural networks [6], enhancing robustness, interpretability, and generalization by integrating system equations into the learning process. This combined focus on data consistency and physical constraints provides effective defense against compromised measurements. In our recent work in [14], we show the potential of PINNs for fast and accurate state estimation in modern power grids. Building on this, in this work we examine the problem of cyber attack mitigation, considering data manipulation attacks, and propose a new PINN model where power injection equations are directly integrated in the loss function and integrating the loss function weights in the parameter tuning process.

A. Physics-Informed Neural Networks

PINNs represent an innovative approach to machine learning that combines data-driven methods with fundamental physical laws. The core principle is simple: while traditional neural networks learn purely from data, PINNs incorporate knowledge of physical laws directly into their learning process. Mathematically, we can express this as a neural network $f(\mathbf{z}; \theta)$ that tries to approximate a target function f , where θ represents the network's adjustable parameters (weights) and \mathbf{z} represents the input variables. The learning process in PINNs is guided by two complementary objectives:

$$\mathcal{L} = w_d \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} + w_p \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}} \quad (4)$$

where weights $w_d, w_p, \in [0, 1]$ are allocated such as $w_d + w_p = 1$, balancing their relative contributions. The data loss term,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \|f(\mathbf{z}_i; \theta) - f_i\|^2 \quad (5)$$

quantifies the discrepancy between model predictions and observed data (\mathbf{z}_i, f_i) , while the physics loss term,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}} = \sum_{j=1}^M \|G(\hat{f}(\mathbf{z}_j; \theta), \mathbf{z}_j)\|^2 \quad (6)$$

ensures compliance with physical laws $G(\hat{f}, \mathbf{z}) = 0$. This dual-objective framework allows PINNs to make predictions that are both data-consistent and physically realistic, even with limited data.

B. Physical Constraints of a Power System

Our PINN model development starts by identifying input-output pairs connected through physics-based relationships, preferably incorporating system constants and/or topology. The model's loss function integrates data fitting and physical constraints, with the model weights optimized based on system characteristics. In power system state estimation, we focus on determining voltage magnitudes (V_i) and phase angles (θ_i) at each bus. The PINN uses net active (P_i) and reactive (Q_i) power injections as inputs to estimate complex voltages as outputs. Leveraging these measurements, along with the equations relating them to complex voltages, reveal system topology through data patterns that the model can extract. The power injections follow these relationships:

$$P_i = V_i \sum_{j \in N} V_j (G_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij} + B_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij}) \quad (7a)$$

$$Q_i = V_i \sum_{j \in N} V_j (G_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij} - B_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij}) \quad (7b)$$

where V_i, V_j are bus voltages, θ_{ij} is the phase angle differences between two buses, G_{ij} and B_{ij} are the admittance matrix components, and N is the total bus number. The admittance matrix captures system topology, allowing the model to infer system structure through power-voltage relationships without explicit architectural constraints imposed on the model or the training procedure.

C. Loss Function Formulation

To formulate the model's objectives as a loss function which will be used by an optimizer we need to combine data and physics into the neural network's loss function, as seen in Eq. 4, where $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$ represents the discrepancy between predicted and actual values, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}}$ encodes physics-based constraints (in this case, the power flow equations). The loss function (denoted as \mathcal{L}) is computed as the sum of the *Mean Square Error (MSE)* between the actual data and the inferred values ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$) and the *MSE* resulting from enforcing a physics equation ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}}$) that should ideally equal zero. The loss function is designed to be minimized during a backpropagation training process, as depicted in Fig. 1.

To establish a baseline NN as a benchmark, the loss function architecture is designed to accommodate both traditional NN and PINN through a hybrid formulation. For a traditional NN, the loss computation focuses solely on the data-driven component, while the PINN incorporates additional physics-based constraints. The hybrid loss function is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \begin{cases} \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} & \text{for data-driven NN} \\ w_d \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} + w_p \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}} & \text{for PINN} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Data loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$ is computed using normalized voltage magnitudes and phase angles, using the training batch's mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ):

$$V' = \frac{V - \mu_V}{\sigma_V + \epsilon}, \quad \theta' = \frac{\theta - \mu_\theta}{\sigma_\theta + \epsilon} \quad (9a)$$

Fig. 1. Model training procedure for power system state estimation.

$$\mathcal{L}_{data} = \text{MSE}(V'_{true} - V'_{est}) + \text{MSE}(\theta'_{true} - \theta'_{est}) \quad (9b)$$

Physics loss $\mathcal{L}_{physics}$ incorporates power flow constraints with normalized active P and reactive Q power values, using the training batch's mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ):

$$P' = \frac{P - \mu_P}{\sigma_P + \epsilon}, \quad Q' = \frac{Q - \mu_Q}{\sigma_Q + \epsilon} \quad (10a)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{physics} = \text{MSE}(P'_{true} - P'_{est}) + \text{MSE}(Q'_{true} - Q'_{est}) \quad (10b)$$

where P_{est} and Q_{est} are derived from Eq. 7 using the estimated voltages (V) and angles (θ). This loss function ensures the model learns effectively from data while respecting physical laws, preventing overfitting and keeping the results realistic.

D. Hyperparameter Optimization

Hyperparameter optimization employed Optuna's Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) [15]. The objective function minimizes a weighted combination of Mean Squared Error (MSE) on data and, for PINNs, physics residuals. Key hyperparameters include network architecture (number of layers and their neurons), batch size, learning rate, and, for PINNs, the physics-data loss weight. The process aimed to balance model complexity, enhance convergence, and ensure robust performance across varied conditions. The optimization trials identified the best hyperparameter configuration, providing a strong foundation for model evaluation and comparison.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

This section details the experimental setup used to train and evaluate the proposed PINN for power system state estimation under various conditions, including cyberattacks. The dataset we utilized represents a 4-day daily load profile of a real-world system adapted to the IEEE 14-bus benchmark system. The voltage/angles were generated using the PowerWorld software. A fixed transmission grid topology with a known admittance matrix ($Y = G + jB$) is assumed, where each bus provides real and reactive power injections. Under normal conditions, full system observability is maintained. The NN and PINN models were implemented in Python with TensorFlow for efficient neural network training. The models' generalization capabilities and its ability to handle real-world uncertainties were enhanced by introducing simulated measurement noise

TABLE I
HYPERPARAMETER OPTIMIZATION SEARCH SPACE

Parameter	Range
Layers (N_l)	{2, 4, 6}
Neurons per layer (N_n)	{64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096}
Batch Size (B)	{4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128}
Learning Rate (η)	$[10^{-5}, 10^{-3}]$ (logarithmically sampled)
Loss weights (w_p)	$[0.1, 0.9]$ (discretized with a step of 0.05)

into our datasets [16], emulating inherent measurement inaccuracies and stochastic fluctuations.

The models' architecture dynamically adjusts hyperparameters, including the number of layers and neurons per layer, which were optimized using TPE within the Optuna framework. All hyperparameter configurations, including the number of layers, neurons per layer, batch size, and learning rate, are detailed in Table I. For the PINN, we additionally optimized the weighting between the physics loss and the data loss, with the data loss weight defined as $w_d = 1 - w_p$. This enabled analysis of the trade-off between enforcing physics constraints and fitting observed data. For the standard NN, the loss reduces to $\mathcal{L}_{NN} = \mathcal{L}_{data}$ with $w_p = 0$ and $w_d = 1$.

Neural network weights were initialized with the Glorot scheme, biases were set to zero, and training capped optimization to 100 epochs. The TPE optimizer was allowed to choose 10 different sets of hyperparameter sets. The Adam optimizer and tanh activation function were employed for all models. The best-performing model (minimizing loss) was selected after a training process was conducted on a GPU-enabled environment. The dataset was split into training and testing sets, at a 70:30 ratio, with various attack scenarios simulated to assess the model's robustness.

B. Testing Scenarios

In this study, we evaluate the performance of both PINN and standard NN under various attack scenarios. Both model types were trained using the same steady-state dataset. To assess the robustness of the PINN and NN models, we modified the testing dataset to simulate an attacker's behavior. Specifically, we assumed the attacker could compromise specific sensors on select buses and inject falsified measurements, as described in Section III-A. The introduced data corruption was quantified using a modification factor a of [5%, 10%, 20%, 30%], representing varying magnitudes of manipulation.

The testing dataset was designed under the premise that the attacker has full control over the (P) and (Q) measurements of

Fig. 2. Model accuracy as measured against an unknown steady state dataset

the compromised buses. In each attack scenario, a single bus was compromised, while all other measurements remained unaffected. The dataset included 1728 test points with the P and Q values modified for the attacked buses. To ensure statistically significant results, the testing dataset was replicated 1000 times (a total of 1728000 test points), each copy containing a slightly different type of attack, varying in bus targeted, and P/Q increase or decrease for each modification factor. These attack scenarios were intended to comprehensively evaluate the models' ability to maintain accurate predictions under diverse levels and types of data corruption, thereby assessing the PINN's robustness in adversarial conditions.

C. Model Evaluation

The proposed PINN-based state estimation model underwent comprehensive evaluation across diverse operational scenarios, encompassing both nominal conditions and simulated adversarial environments. The experimental results, summarized in Table II, provide an overview of the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and the coefficient of determination (R-Squared), as measured across the full inferred SE values of each model.

Under steady-state conditions, the MAE curves illustrated in Figure 2 reveal critical performance differentials between the PINN and the conventional NN. Both models demonstrate stable convergence during training; however, the PINN distinguishes itself through substantially improved accuracy metrics. Specifically, the MAE analysis reveals that the PINN outperforms the traditional NN by approximately 56% in state estimation functionality.

The residual analysis further substantiates the PINN's superior performance. Box plots in Figure 2 show the statistical distribution of residuals, where the PINN exhibits tighter clustering around the median. In contrast, the conventional NN produces significantly more outliers and a considerably wider residual spread. Per-bus accuracy measurements reinforce this observation, with the PINN consistently demonstrating more precise and consistent estimations.

The framework's resilience was rigorously tested under adversarial conditions, as outlined in Sections III-A and V-B. Figure 3 visualizes the probabilistic residual distributions across various attack scenarios. While both models experience performance degradation under adversarial data manipulation, the PINN demonstrates greater robustness, exhibiting less of a performance decline compared to the conventional NN.

TABLE II
MODEL COMPARISON

Scenario	Mean Absolute Error		Root Mean Squared Error		R-Squared	
	PINN	NN	PINN	NN	PINN	NN
Steady State	$1.28e-3$	$2.91e-3$	$1.70e-3$	$3.70e-3$	0.9994	0.9968
5%	$7.07e-3$	$1.12e-2$	$8.70e-3$	$1.34e-2$	0.9794	0.9539
10%	$1.40e-2$	$2.19e-2$	$1.71e-2$	$2.60e-2$	0.9134	0.8235
20%	$2.79e-2$	$4.39e-2$	$3.41e-2$	$5.23e-2$	0.6796	0.2779
30%	$4.18e-2$	$6.65e-2$	$5.10e-2$	$8.00e-2$	0.2805	-0.7167

Probability distribution analyses of estimation errors reveal the PINN's superior capability in estimating voltage magnitudes and angles across all the tested adversarial scenarios. The error distributions exhibit higher frequency and tighter concentration around the zero point, indicative of more accurate and consistent estimations. Irrespective of deviation magnitude, the PINN consistently outperforms the traditional NN in maintaining estimation accuracy.

Overall, these findings underscore the benefits of embedding physical constraints within a machine learning model. By effectively leveraging domain knowledge, the PINN not only achieves improved accuracy and stability under normal operating conditions but also demonstrates enhanced robustness in the presence of adversarial data. This comparison against a conventional NN confirms that the PINN is well-suited for applications requiring reliable and precise state estimation in dynamic and potentially compromised environments.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a PINN-based state estimation framework designed to enhance the robustness of power transmission systems against malicious data injection attacks. By integrating power system physics into the neural network architecture, the proposed approach leverages both data-driven insights and physical constraints, leading to improved robustness and accuracy compared to traditional and purely data-driven methods. We developed a PINN model trained on steady-state power system data and systematically evaluated its performance under diverse attack scenarios, including varying magnitudes and attack strategies. Our results demonstrate that the PINN-based approach significantly enhances accuracy and robustness against attacks, surpassing traditional machine learning models, including during disruptions. Importantly, our experiments show that PINNs maintain superior performance under attack by leveraging physical constraints for robustness.

This work contributes to the growing body of research on integrating data-driven and physics-based methodologies, demonstrating the potential of PINNs to address the dynamic

Fig. 3. Adversarial Scenarios: - Residual frequency distributions under modification factor $a = [5\%, 10\%, 20\%, 30\%]$

challenges of modern power systems. By embedding physical laws directly into the neural network architecture and systematically optimizing the model and hyperparameters, PINNs can enhance the accuracy of power system state estimation. Future research directions include extending this framework to dynamic state estimation, incorporating uncertainties in system parameters and measurements, and investigating the robustness of PINNs against other sophisticated cyberattacks.

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